

Sum of Successive Partitions of Binomial Coefficient

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Abstract: This paper focuses on the successive partition method applied to a binomial coefficient in combinatorial geometric series. The coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-13]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, binomial identities and multinomial theorem is provided using the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-13] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

Here, $V_0^1 = 1; V_1^1 = 2; V_2^1 = 3; V_3^1 = 4; V_4^1 = 5; V_5^1 = 6; \dots$

$N = \{V_0^1, V_1^1, V_2^1, V_3^1, V_4^1, V_4^1, \dots\}$ is a set of natural numbers.

$V_n^r = V_r^n, (n, r > 0$ and $n, r \in N)$ is an important binomial identity.

3. Partition of Binomial Coefficient

Let $Q = \{V_1^1, V_2^1, V_3^1, V_4^1, V_4^1, \dots\}$ and Q is contained in N , i.e. $Q \subseteq N$.

The sum of partition of V_n^r is give below:

$$V_n^r = V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1}, (n, r \geq 1 \ \& \ n, r \in N).$$

Prove that V_n^r belongs to Q by successive partitions, i.e. $V_n^r \in Q$, ($n, r \geq 1$ & $n, r \in N$).

Proof. Here, $Q = \{V_1^1, V_2^1, V_3^1, V_4^1, V_4^1, \dots\}$ and Q is contained in N , i.e. $Q \subseteq N$.

$V_2^2 = V_2^1 + V_2^1 = 2V_2^1$. Since $V_2^1 \in Q, V_2^2 \in Q$.

$V_3^2 = V_3^1 + V_2^2 = V_3^1 + 2V_2^1$. Since $V_3^1 \in Q$ and $V_2^1 \in Q, V_3^2 \in Q$.

$V_3^3 = V_3^2 + V_3^2 = 2V_3^2 + 4V_2^1$. Since $V_3^1 \in Q$ and $V_2^1 \in Q, V_3^2 \in Q$.

Similarly, if we can continue these partitions up to V_n^r . Then,

the partitions of V_n^r are in the form of pV_s^1 and $qV_t^1 (= qV_t^1)$ for $p, q, s, t = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$

Since $V_s^1 \in Q$ and $V_t^1 \in Q, V_n^r \in Q$.

Hence, $V_n^r \in Q$, ($n, r \geq 1$ & $n, r \in N$) is proved.

4. Conclusion

In this article, partitions of a binomial coefficient has been introduced and this idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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